

Foresee the Likelihood of Covid-19 Using Chest X-Ray Images with Image Preprocessing

Aneeta Thomas,

PG Scholar of Amal Jyothi College of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, Kerala
aneetathomas@mca.ajce.in

Mr. T.J Jobin

Asst. Professor of Amal Jyothi College Of
Engineering, Kanjirappally, Kerala
tjjobin@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract: Abstract: data mining skills concerned in medical specialty sciences and investigate for providing prediction for facilitate to spot the decease and classify it properly. Screening giant numbers of according cases for no-hit isolation and treatment may be a priority to manage the unfold of Corona Virus (COVID-19). unhealthful laboratory testing is that the scientific gold normal however, given vital false-negative results, and it takes long time. This research paper demonstrates the analysis of Corona Virus decease supported a CNN (convolutional neural network) probabilistic model base on machine learning. The new innovative technology tried to form a deep learning algorithmic program that might extract the graphical characteristics of COVID19 to produce a pre-pathogenic clinical identification and therefore save crucial time for sickness management. It is introduced to develop and take a look at new computer aided identification (CAD) it uses chest x-ray pictures to sight the presence of covid-19 virus. The projected the results of CT-images-CNN classification on CT-images dataset (dataset collected from the web access Kaggle benchmark dataset) are going to be analyse victimisation the convolution neural network in weka software system data processing.

Keywords: Weka, K-means-algorithm, J48-algorithm, Covid-19, CNN.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. DATA MINING

Data mining may be a method utilized by

[10.5281/zenodo.5101223](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5101223)

ISBN:978-93-5426-386-6@2021 MCA, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

organizations to show data into helpful info. By victimisation software system to seem for patterns in giant batches of knowledge, businesses will learn additional regarding their customers to develop more practical selling ways, increase sales and reduce prices.

Data processing depends on effective knowledge assortment, warehousing, and laptop process.

Data mining is that the analysis step of the "knowledge discovery in databases" method, or KDD.

B. WEKA TOOL

Weka is an assortment of machine learning algorithms for data processing tasks.

The algorithms will either be applied on to a dataset or known as from your own Java code.

Named once a wingless New Zealand bird, rail may be a set of machine learning algorithms which will be applied to an information set directly, or known as from your own Java code. Weka contains tools for knowledge pre-processing, classification, regression, clustering, association rules, and visual image. Weka includes many algorithms that we elect classification for the prediction of knowledge results. And here the information is kept in arff format that stands for attribute relation file format. The person that is one in all the interface in rail programme consists of half-dozen panels and every of them having their own task for data processing.

C. WEKA IS A COLLECTION OF TOOLS FOR

- Regression
- Clustering

- **Association**
- **Data pre-processing**
- **Classification**
- **Visualization**
- **Simple CLI**

provides a straightforward command-line interface and permits direct execution of weka commands.

- **Explorer** is a platform for discovering data.

- **Experimenter** is a platform for execute experiments and steering statistical tests among learning schemes.
- **KnowledgeFlow** is a Java-Beans-based interface for setting up and running machine learning experiments.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Rasheed et al. [1] introduced a survey paper investigated medical and technical viewpoints within the battle against the epidemic of COVID-19, which can support virologists, IA researchers and policy-makers. The paper moreover mentioned

[10.5281/zenodo.5101223](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5101223)

ISBN:978-93-5426-386-6@2021 MCA, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

and understood the usage of varied technical instruments and techniques among COVID-19.

The deep learning COVID 19 (COVID Net) model, which had an accuracy of 92.4%, was proposed by Wang and Wong [2] to describe groups as regular, non-COVID, and COVID-19.

Sethy and Behera [3] have known the options mined from varied CNN model's victimisation X-ray pictures and utilized a support vector machine (SVM). Their analysis notes the very best results of the ResNet50 model with the SVM classifier. Finally, some topical COVID-19 experiments utilized a variety of CT image deep learning representations.

Researchers have recommended that comparison clinical imaging findings with laboratory tests can enable to identify COVID-19 early. The analytic info in photography pictures collected from COVID-19 patients is effective. many reports have specified improvements before the consequences of COVID-19 began supported chest X-rays and CT scans.

Researchers have furthermore created vivacious advances in COVID-19 imaging analysis in a very COVID-19 case, Kong et al. [4] noted right-sided ground glass opaqueness.

Yoon et al. [5] found one nodular opacity inside the lowerleft respiratory organ space in one out of 3 examined patients. The opposite 2 patients, by comparison, showed irregular hardness between respiratory organ areas four and 5.

Elaziz MA. et al. [6] recommended a COVID-19 machine learning procedure to classify X-ray pictures of the chest into 2 groups: COVID-19 or non-COVID-19 patients. Their model used a FrMEMs methodology to take benefit of the options from chest X-ray pictures.

To accelerate the procedure method, a parallel multi-core procedure design was used. Then, the foremost vital options were elect victimisation changed devilfish hunt improvement supported differential evolution.

This research paper establishes the analysis of Corona Virus sickness supported a CNN (convolutional neural network) probabilistic model based on machine learning. The CSV file of 2002 x-ray Dataset to patients from Kaggle.com loaded to the weka tool. the information needed for this analysis is downloaded from Kaggle benchmark information web site.

III. PROPOSED WORK

Firstly, download this weka tool. once the install is finished, we can launch Weka.

For analysing data set results, we must need a corresponding data set. That we can either create using java code or we can download it directly from internet. (downloadable data set can be find in website: Kaggle benchmark dataset). From there we can download the dataset contains chest x-ray images of patients who have been affected with disease as covid-19 and normal cases (for specifically finding the covid patients)

The downloaded data set will be in an excel sheet. Next, we just have to save it as in csv format. After saving it in csv format we can open that file in weka, it will perform all the analysis in the tool only if it is in arff format. For that we must have to do some work on our csv file data.

For converting it into arff format we should open the **experimenter** tab shown in the GUI of weka. Then choose option **analyse** option. Then click on file. Then open the csv file the save it as. arff in the directory which the weka file is stored. So far, we've got the proper data set so now we are ready to go.

Step 1: Open the arff data in workbench: pre-processing

Here our first tab is **preprocess**. This is nothing but it will load the data set and manipulate the data into a form that you want to work with. Here we can see the count of instances, attributes and its weights. Also, as we can see there is a pictorial representation of data which is shown in red and blue colour. The blue indicates the count of covid positive cases and red indicates covid negative cases.

Step 2: Classify the data using decision tree algorithm: J48

As we can see here working algorithm is J48 (we choose this algorithm for classification of our data set for understanding the accuracy of our data. And it also classifies the data firmly and thus it will give a tree structure of our data. Here we find out that in our data set there are 1400 correctly classified instances. Which means the accuracy of our data result is 99% accurate.

Also, there is a confusion Matrix which shows a sample data which indicate which one is normal image and which one is affected by covid virus.

Also, if we want to see this result in a tree structure we just only need to right click on the trees. J48(highlighted). It will be like following figure:

Step 3: Cluster the data using Simple k-means algorithm

We cluster the data set using Simple K-means algorithm. We are using this algorithm for grouping similar data points in our larger dataset without concern for the specific outcome. Here in the above figure, we can see the clustered instances as an evaluation of the algorithm.

Step 4: Associate the data using FilteredAssociator Algorithm

We perform associate operation in the data result for extract insights from data set. And also, it will find associations between attributes.

Step 5: Select Attributes

In here this property is used for data reduction in our data mining process. Which means this will reduce the size of the data so that it can be used for analysis purposes more efficiently. This process is get done because of the huge size of our data set.

Step 6: Visualize the data result

This will provide us a scattered plotter Metrix for review. Blue color indicates the covid-19 cases and red color represents normal cases.

And if we want to see the representation further more clear we can double click on the respective column for more visualization. It will be shown in following figure. The technique of representing data through graphs and plots with the purpose to recognize data clearly is data visualization.

Data visualization using WEKA is shortened with the assistance of the box plot. The user can view any level of roughness. The attributes are plotted on X-axis and y-axis while the instances are plotted against the X and Y-axis.

Data Visualization in WEKA can be achieved on all datasets in the WEKA directory. The raw dataset can be viewed as well as other succeeding datasets of other algorithms such as classification, clustering, and association can be visualized using WEKA.

Advantages & Disadvantages

Advantages:

- Open-source-software.
- Simple and easy to use
- Gives a precise classify of x-ray-Images of COVID19 between viral and normal cases.
- Gives more accurate results within seconds.

Disadvantages

- X-ray image preprocessing is more costly than analysing a blood sample.

10.5281/zenodo.5101223

ISBN:978-93-5426-386-6@2021 MCA, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

IV. IMPLIMENTATION

In current situation our traditional golden method of analyzing blood or saliva sample of a patient can gives us the result of covid testing.

But there may be the chance of getting wrong results to wrong person and it also takes more time for analyzing the sample. The implementation is that we can collect the x-ray images of the patients from a hospital database and can preprocess the images with the help of weka tool to detect whether that patient is affected by covid-19 virus or not. Since it is a machine learning tool, we can have our test results within seconds.

V. RESULT

The given test data is given to the tool for preprocessing.

Through each process of image classifications, the images are getting preprocessed and the taken algorithms [J48, K-means] will analyses the test results and will gives a proper analysis of data that is how much accurate the data classification is.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, the author aims to early diagnosis of covid19 by using a benchmark x-ray Images dataset on our proposed grouping of four image filters with composed hybrid feature selection (CHFS) model. Using the results of filter approaches as some preceding information with using the J48 decision tree classifier as a suitability function and random selection to accelerate merging and select the best features with compare of modifying a innovative CNN structure The proposed CNN model shows healthier than the traditional classification methods for ideal feature selection and enhancement of the classification process and effectively abridged the false-negative rate with high accuracy with 99.64% compared to 77.31% of usage traditional classifiers.

VII. FUTURE WORK

This outstanding technology can be implemented in any hospital or clinics which will be a great step towards fast and accurate patient analysis.

Any person who comes up with any decease also can be tested for covid-19 without the traditional sample testing. The covid-19 detection can be analyzed automatically with the help of exceptional machine learning algorithms.

VIII. REFERENCES

[1] Rasheed J., Jamil A., Hameed A. A., Aftab U., Aftab J., Shah S. A., et al., "An investigation on artificial intelligence methods in supporting frontline workers and decision makers for COVID-19 pandemic," *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, p. 110337, 2020. doi: 10.1016/j.chaos.2020.110337. PMID:33071481

[2] L. a. W. Wang, A, "COVID-Net: A Tailored Deep Convolutional Neural Network Design for Detection of COVID-19 Cases from Chest X-Ray Images.," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2003.09871*, 2020.

[3] Sethy P. K. and Behera S. K., "Detection of coronavirus disease (covid-19) based on deep features," *Preprints*, vol. 2020030300, p. 2020, 2020.

[4] Kong W. and Agarwal P. P., "Chest imaging appearance of COVID-19

infection," *Radiology: Cardiothoracic Imaging*, vol. 2, p. e200028, 2020.

[5] Yoon S. H., Lee K. H., Kim J. Y., Lee Y. K., Ko H., Kim K. H., et al., "Chest radiographic and CT findings of the 2019 novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19): analysis of nine patients treated in Korea," *Korean journal of radiology*, vol. 21, pp. 494–500, 2020.

[6] Elaziz M. A., Hosny K. M., Salah A., Darwish M. M., Lu S., and Sahlol A. T., "New machine learning method for image-based analysis of COVID-19," *Plos one*, vol. 15, p. e0235187, 2020. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0235187. PMID:32589673